

Growing a high-level roadmap for open fusion energy sciences¹

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Project Summary

Fusion energy has the potential for safe, clean, and abundant energy in the coming decades with virtually no greenhouse gas emissions. Although significant progress toward fusion has been made in the last few years, a major barrier to bringing fusion energy to the grid is the lack of adoption of open science practices. Unlike fields such as heliophysics and astronomy, few research facilities have made their data archives openly available. Closed data management and related practices inhibit research and constitute a barrier to access into the field. To address this problem and promote open science in fusion energy, I propose to perform three tasks. First, I will gather colleagues to collaboratively develop a high-level open science roadmap for fusion energy. Second, I will record and release podcast episodes to promote open fusion energy science and this roadmap. Third, I will perform a baseline of maintenance for PlasmaPy: an open source core Python package for plasma research and education.

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Project Description

Fusion energy holds the promise of a safe, clean, and effectively inexhaustible source of power. Fusion power plants will produce essentially no greenhouse gas emissions during operation. Unlike fission power plants, fusion power yields no high-level radioactive waste and has zero chance of a catastrophic meltdown. The high energy density of the deuterium-tritium fuel means that fusion power plants will require a much smaller land footprint than wind & solar farms, and will not significantly disrupt local ecosystems like hydroelectric power. While fusion power has been actively investigated for ~70 years, several more decades of scientific and engineering research are needed to bring fusion power to the grid (NASEM 2019, 2021).

There are two leading strategies for achieving fusion energy: magnetic fusion energy (MFE) and inertial confinement fusion (ICF). MFE devices such as tokamaks use strong magnetic fields to confine plasma and achieve sufficiently high temperatures and densities for fusion to occur. Technical challenges for MFE include controlling plasma instabilities, sustaining plasma confinement, and managing heat loads and neutron fluxes on the reactor walls. ICF facilities like the National Ignition Facility (NIF) use lasers to rapidly compress deuterium-tritium capsules to produce high energy density plasma. Challenges include symmetric compression of the fuel pellet, economical target fabrication, and achieving higher repetition rates. Despite the technical challenges, researchers have broken records multiple times in the last few years. The KSTAR tokamak in South Korea set the record for confining fusion plasma for 30 s in 2021 and then 48 s in 2024 (Ko et al. 2024). The JET tokamak in the UK produced a record 69 MJ in 2024, and multiple shots at the National Ignition Facility (NIF) since 2021 have exceeded the Lawson (1957) criterion for fusion ignition (Abu-Shawareb et al. 2022). When the International Thermonuclear Experimental Reactor becomes the world's largest operational tokamak, even more records are hoped to be broken.

However, technical challenges are not the only barriers to achieving fusion energy. While practices like community development of open source software and open sharing of data have gained traction in fields like heliophysics and astronomy, closed science practices remain entrenched in the fusion energy sciences community (Murphy 2023). In solar physics, most observational data sets are openly available. The Virtual Solar Observatory (VSO) lets us simultaneously search multiple data archives and then download observational data from multiple sources. The solar physics community has a long history of collaboratively developing open source software such as SunPy (SunPy Community 2023). SunPy and VSO let anyone with a sufficient internet connection to download observations of their favorite solar flare within minutes. In contrast, the vast majority of experimental data from fusion devices is restricted by

institutions, and there is no web portal like VSO that would allow us to simultaneously search for experimental data from multiple facilities.

The fusion community lacks the culture and technical infrastructure for open sharing of software and data (Murphy 2023). **However, recent efforts on multiple continents show that the fusion community is on the cusp of change.** FAIR4Fusion laid the groundwork for applying the FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable) principles for stewardship of scientific data (Wilkinson et al. 2016) to Eurofusion data. Moreover, data from two fusion devices – the Large Helical Device in Japan and MAST in the UK – recently began making their experimental data sets openly available.

I began my efforts to make plasma science open ~8 years ago when I founded the PlasmaPy project, which is fostering the growth of a fully open source Python ecosystem for plasma research and education. PlasmaPy itself (PlasmaPy Community et al. 2024) contains core functionality for plasma science and has had 147 contributors. PlasmaPy was directly inspired by SunPy and Astropy. We held the inaugural PlasmaPy Summer School this summer to provide opportunities for students, scientists, and educators to learn how to contribute to an open source package such as PlasmaPy.

Over the past few years, I have presented on making plasma science open and reproducible at multiple plasma conferences and fusion summer schools (e.g., Murphy 2023). In the resulting discussions, the emerging generation of plasma scientists has been very supportive of open science principles. However, only a few of the students and scientists who I have talked with have a clear understanding of how to apply open science principles in practice. While agencies like NASA have investigated and adopted open science policies (e.g., NASEM 2018a), the Department of Energy (DOE) Office of Fusion Energy Sciences has done little to promote open science. The fusion community lacks a cohesive strategy for open science, which has resulted in piecemeal efforts and limited progress. To address this deficiency, I propose to promote open fusion science via the following tasks.

Task #1: Collaboratively develop a high-level roadmap for open science and knowledge equity in fusion energy. I will invite colleagues from the fusion community who have been working towards open science and diversity, equity, inclusion, and accessibility (DEIA) to join with representatives from different facilities and develop a high-level plan for making fusion energy sciences open. We will assess the current fusion landscape including the culture & climate, efforts toward DEIA, the data & software environments, and ongoing work to make fusion science open. We will review

prior work in fusion and adjacent fields (e.g., Murphy et al. 2017, 2019; Płóciennik 2022; Murphy 2023) and recent reports (NASEM 2018a, 2018b, 2019, 2021) to identify opportunities and unique challenges. We will split into working groups such as open access data, open source software, open hardware, educational resources, public engagement, and open publication. The roadmap will describe potential linkages between different topical areas. For example, metadata standards could be applied to newly open data sets with corresponding readers being implemented in PlasmaPy. Because plasma science has historically had one of the worst DEIA track records in physics, the roadmap must identify evidence-based practices to improve the culture & climate (e.g., human relation codes, bias incident policies, and psychological safety training). We will develop this roadmap openly on GitHub under the PlasmaPy organization and make it publicly available via GitHub pages so that the broader community can review and contribute to it, including after this project concludes. We will submit version 1.0 of the roadmap for open access publication and introduce the roadmap to DOE program managers. I will submit an abstract for an hour-long tutorial talk on this roadmap at a large plasma physics conference.

Task #2: Record pilot episodes of a podcast to promote open fusion energy science. While roadmap documents will be a valuable community resource, we will further grow support for open fusion energy science via podcast interviews. After taking professional development time to learn the necessary podcasting skills, I will create the podcast infrastructure under the PlasmaPy organization using the openpodcast tech stack. Potential interviewees include Royce James on DEIA in fusion, Aditi Verma on engaging local communities, Nathan Cummings on making tokamak data open access, and Sumana Harihareswara on software sustainability. While working on the initial episodes, I will set up the infrastructure so that other members of the collaboration can release episodes. Creating pilot episodes will allow us to include this podcast as a broader impact in future grant proposals.

Task #3: Provide a baseline of maintenance for PlasmaPy. My contributions to PlasmaPy are supported by an NSF award that is projected to conclude around March 2025. In case of a funding gap while waiting to hear back about proposals, I propose to perform baseline maintenance for PlasmaPy to sustain the project. Specific tasks include helping new contributors, fixing bugs, leading virtual tutorials, performing official releases.

Broader Impact, Outreach, and Educational Plan

Forging a high-level roadmap for open fusion energy science strongly aligns with both the *Life on a Sustainable Planet* initiative and the Smithsonian Institution's overall purpose: the increase and diffusion of knowledge. Fusion energy has the potential to provide abundant energy with minimal greenhouse emissions and a lower environmental impact than other forms of renewable energy. A community-developed roadmap for open fusion energy sciences has the potential to speed up the process of bringing fusion power to the grid, which would in turn allow reductions of greenhouse emissions worldwide. Making knowledge about fusion energy openly available will increase knowledge equity and allow faster worldwide adoption of fusion energy than if the knowledge is kept proprietary. Inviting members of the fusion community to collaboratively develop this roadmap and using non-traditional forms of science communication such as podcasts increases the likelihood that this project will cultivate an open fusion science community of practice.

Open science itself has numerous benefits (NASEM 2018b). Open science reduces barriers to accessing knowledge and makes it so that under-resourced institutions have more equitable access to research tools and more equitable participation in their development. Open science improves the quality of research through improved computational reproducibility and a higher likelihood that errors and bugs will be spotted. Open science can also enable research that would not be performed otherwise. Right now, machine learning studies for fusion are particularly challenging because acquiring and wrangling data from multiple facilities is very difficult. The roadmap will necessarily include plans for open educational resources, with potential linkages to software documentation that describes the underlying physics.

Project Timeline

April – May 2025

- Identify & invite potential collaborators on open fusion science roadmap.
- Begin holding weekly virtual collaboration meetings.
- Perform literature review and assess current status of open science and knowledge equity in fusion energy.
- Confirm major topical areas for roadmap (e.g., data environment, software environment, culture & climate, and education).
- Initialize website for roadmap using the Hugo static site generator and GitHub pages.

- Engage in professional development to learn necessary podcasting skills, including how to use the openpodcast framework.
- Begin developing podcast infrastructure, including a page on the PlasmaPy website.
- Perform baseline maintenance for PlasmaPy if no other funding source is available.

June – July 2025

- Hold working group meetings for the major topical areas for the roadmap.
- Begin drafting sections for roadmap topical areas.
- Submit abstract for an hour-long tutorial talk entitled *Making plasma science open* for the American Physical Society (APS) Division of Plasma Physics (DPP) meeting.
- Record and edit first podcast interview.
- Perform baseline maintenance for PlasmaPy if no other funding source is available.

August – September 2025

- Complete sections of roadmap topical areas.
- Review and edit the first full draft of the roadmap.
- Record and edit ~2 podcast interviews.
- Perform baseline maintenance for PlasmaPy if no other funding source is available.

October – November 2025

- Submit an open access journal article of the roadmap to *Journal of Plasma Physics*.
- Address referee comments on roadmap articles.
- Record and edit ~2 podcast interviews.
- Release remaining podcast episodes.
- Attend and present on the roadmap at the APS DPP meeting.
- Perform baseline maintenance for PlasmaPy if no other funding source is available.

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